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TESTUDO

AUTONOMOUS SWARM OF HETEROGENEOUS RESOURCES
IN INFRASTRUCTURE PROTECTION VIA THREAT PREDICTION AND PREVENTION

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TESTUDO will deliver a novel data-driven and process-oriented surveillance and intelligence platform for increased autonomy and improved situation awareness, incorporating:

- 🔧 **innovative autonomous platforms** comprised by a set of **unmanned vehicles** and individual **fixed sensors**,
- 🔧 effective transmission of **heterogeneous multimodal data streams** to improve the critical issue for smooth operations and the integrity of CIs,
- 🔧 **advanced detection, monitoring and prediction tools** delivering pertinent information to the operator,
- 🔧 **virtual decision-making tool.**

TESTUDO aims to equip CI operators and other relevant agencies with innovative technologies reinforced with research tools for **optimal response and prediction/prevention**, by employing:

🔧 **Autonomous Response and Cognitive Intelligence**

- 🔧 Optimal resource allocation
- 🔧 Threat identification by processing optronics data
- 🔧 Edge computing for limited connected unmanned vehicles
- 🔧 CBRN materials identification
- 🔧 Autonomous response on cyber-attack identifications

🔧 **Improved HMI for critical infrastructure surveillance**

- 🔧 Optimized 3D terrain and infrastructure mapping
- 🔧 Fusion schemes of numerous modalities for improved data representation
- 🔧 Threat assessment via XAI technologies
- 🔧 Predictive intelligence and improved HMI via Digital Twins

🔧 **Short and long-term deployment for large-scale and cross-sectorial trials**

Use Case #1:
Disruptive online events
in water reservoirs

Use Case #2:
Chemical fire in tunnel provoked
by an electric vehicle

Use Case #3:
Synchronized attack
on water treatment facilities

TESTUDO ARCHITECTURE

Predictive intelligence and decision support

Predictive Decision Making
via Digital Twins

XAI for threat assessment

Multi-modal fusion

Improved HMI
in a Monitoring Centre

XR Technologies

Cognitive intelligence for threat identification

 CBRNE material detection

 Cyber-threat detection

Optimised 3D
terrain and facilities

Autonomous Resource Allocation

Autonomous Vehicle Navigation

 Low-altitude
aerial vehicles High-altitude
aerial vehicles Unmanned
ground vehicles

Sensor for Autonomous Surveillance

 CCTV
cameras Thermal
cameras 360
cameras CBRNE
sensor IoT sensors
(LiDAR etc)

TESTUDO

Start date	01/10/2023
End date	30/09/2026
Call	HORIZON-CL3-2022-INFRA-01-02
Partners	20
Countries	11
Project Coordinator	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH)

TESTUDO PARTNERS

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